

IMPROVING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE THROUGH INTERNET APPLICATIONS (as an example of the Duolingo app)

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Abstract: Utilizing technology to make teaching more engaging is necessary due to the myriad of issues facing education today. A different approach to assisting students in learning vocabulary in a targeted language is through technology. The development of not only rich communicative competence, but also reading, listening, and writing skills in students is largely dependent on their vocabulary. To help students with their English vocabulary, one of the apps that helped them is Duolingo. This article is devoted to going over and examining prior research on this topic and highlighting benefits of the Duolingo app.

Keywords: curriculum, Duolingo, applications, language acquisition, language proficiency.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda ta'lim oldida turgan ko'plab muammolar tufayli o'qitishni yanada qiziqarli qilish uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish zarur. Talabalarga maqsadli tilda lug'atni o'rganishda yordam berishning boshqacha yondashuvi texnologiyadir. O'quvchilarda nafaqat boy kommunikativ kompetensiyani, balki o'qish, tinglash va yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish ko'p jihatdan ularning so'z boyligiga bog'liq. Talabalarga ingliz tilidagi so'z boyligida yordam berish uchun ularga yordam bergan ilovalardan biri Duolingo. Maqola ushbu mavzu bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning tahlili va Duolingo ilovasining afzalliklari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quv dasturi, Duolingo, ilovalar, til o'zlashtirish, tilni bilish.

Аннотация: Использование технологий, чтобы сделать обучение более увлекательным, необходимо из-за множества проблем, стоящих сегодня перед образованием. Другой подход к помощи учащимся в изучении словарного запаса на изучаемом языке заключается в использовании технологий. Развитие не только богатой коммуникативной компетентности, но и навыков чтения, аудирования и письма у учащихся во многом зависит от их словарного запаса. Чтобы помочь студентам пополнить словарный запас английского языка, им помогло одно из приложений — Duolingo. Эта статья посвящена обзору предыдущих исследований по этой теме и выделению преимуществ приложения Duolingo.

Ключевые слова: учебная программа, Duolingo, приложения, изучение языка, знание языка.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technology has produced what are now referred to as "Educational Technologies" and has improved education in many ways. Technology and language have become closely entwined. Technology is also advancing in marketing practice and education. For instance, for the past few years, the internet has experienced exponential growth. Furthermore, ownership, connectivity, and access to technology are crucial objectives of achievement for implementing mobile learning in higher education. Teachers can enhance their teaching methods and education by utilizing technology as a tool. Especially when teaching English vocabulary and developing students' speaking skills, the instructor should make the best use of technology to assist those who are struggling with a language. One essential component of interactive learning that students find acceptable is using technology to acquire English. The majority are familiar with a variety of technological elements, such as gadgets, applications, and social media, so they can welcome the idea of using them for educational purposes. Since technology is a part of daily life, it is time to reconsider how to include it in the curriculum and how to use it in the classroom to aid in the teaching and learning process. As a result, technology has become a crucial component of education and a major concern for educators, from planning lessons to carrying out the teaching and learning process.

METHODS

While conducting this research, qualitative and secondary data analysis methods were used. Technology-based educational games can be used in a variety of ways to enhance English teaching and learning activities. Learning has been aided by instructional games more and more in recent years. The activities have benefits including fostering spontaneous and innovative language use and improving communication ability. Furthermore, it can effectively boost motivation and encourage a learner-centered approach, enabling students to enhance their English language proficiency both within and beyond the classroom. One tool that can be used to increase vocabulary in foreign languages is Duolingo. A laptop, smartphone, or website can all be used to access the free app Duolingo. It helps pupils increase their vocabulary in English. Not only does it assist students in focusing on enriching their vocabulary in English, but it also can draw students in and actively engage them in the teaching process. Duolingo was founded by Luis Von Ahn and Severin Hacker as a freemium language-learning app for computers and smartphones in 2012. It provides 68 distinct language courses in 28 different languages. According to the Duolingo website, teaching students the four English language skills of reading,

writing, speaking, and listening is made simple for teachers by the Duolingo application as four skills are covered in Duolingo the learning activities through questions, spoken small text, and transcriptions. To evaluate their speaking proficiency, the students ought to record their pronunciation. Duolingo offers a variety of learning exercises, namely:

❖ *Translation*

The first exercise is called "translation," in which learners or students translate their existing knowledge into the language they wish to learn and the other way around. Matching is the second exercise, in which students should match the word provided with the picture on Duolingo, or vice versa.

❖ *Pairing exercise*

The third exercise is the pairing exercise. Learners are required to match up appropriately between an equal number of words from two languages in the pairing exercise.

❖ **Listening**

The fourth exercise is listening, when Duolingo plays a brief sentence in the language students are planning to learn, and they ought to type it accurately.

Speak this sentence

❖ **Speaking**

In the fifth activity, which involves speaking, students listen to sentences in the language they have learned and then repeat what they have heard. In addition to all of those exercises, the Duolingo app offers users the option to return to any lesson level they choose, even after they have completed every level.

However, grammar is not available on the app, as it only focuses on vocabulary-focused exercises, which are meant to improve language learning objectives. Nonetheless, grammar instruction is still accessible through this app by simply stating whether the learner's response is right or wrong after responding.

According to previous studies, Duolingo offers its users a variety of advantages, including:

- ✚ It exposes users to a wide variety of terminology that helps to enrich their vocabulary.
- ✚ It helps users recognize and use different kinds of sentence patterns that support improved comprehension and grammar proficiency.
- ✚ By doing the Duolingo exercises, individuals are trained to improve their speaking, listening, reading, and writing abilities.
- ✚ By giving users the chance to compete with one another, it motivates them to be more active.
- ✚ It incorporates the gamification concept, which keeps users engaged and motivated to learn the language, to create an enjoyable and engaging learning environment.

RESULTS

The purpose of this study is to find out how students feel about using the Duolingo app to learn English. According to the survey, 90% of participants have laptops and every participant has an Android or smartphone. They had been in use for two to three years. They are all also using laptops or mobile phones with Duolingo accounts. The researcher or the lecturer recommended at the start of the semester that the participants use Duolingo for at least 15 minutes a day for play and learning. As the instructor had advised, some individuals didn't open Duolingo (7.4%). Thankfully, a lot of students used Duolingo for more than 15 minutes a day or more than two hours a week to play and learn (60.7%).

According to given pie chart above, it is indicated that students have a favorable attitude toward using the Duolingo app to study English. The means for every item ranged from 3.51 to 4.50, all of which were high.

DISCUSSION

It has been discovered that Duolingo helps with language acquisition and reduces speaking anxiety. Speaking anxiety was lower in the experimental group which used Duolingo than in the control group, according to a study done on second-year preparatory school students. Furthermore, a group of app users expressed greater delight in learning a foreign language, suggesting that Duolingo increased their enthusiasm and involvement in language acquisition. Having said that, there is a negative relationship between speaking performance and anxiety, indicating that lowering anxiety can enhance speaking abilities. Anxiety negatively impacted the speaking competency of students enrolled in English Conversation Class Level II, namely in terms of their capacity to communicate and connect with others. These results demonstrate how crucial it is to deal with speaking anxiety when learning a language and the possible advantages of using Duolingo as a technique to reduce anxiety and improve speaking abilities.

CONCLUSION

The Duolingo app will make the language-learning process more engaging and joyful. Thus, it can advance students' vocabulary learning in English. The paper concludes that students see using Duolingo to learn English, particularly vocabulary, favorably. It can improve, make students feel at ease, make learning enjoyable, and inspire them to learn more English, all of which are major advantages for supporting students' learning. One tool that encourages learning English is Duolingo, which is also a useful tool for students looking to improve their English language proficiency. Duolingo has the potential to enhance students' engagement and inspire them to

acquire English language skills, hence yielding favorable outcomes for their academic performance. One benefit of the Duolingo app is that it can help kids succeed academically by providing them with specialized subject teaching that is reinforced with particular activities. Furthermore, both teachers and students are realizing how beneficial internet resources can be in bolstering in-person activities. Students' learning might be aided by this application, which would help them achieve more. In addition, a lot of students think that learning English with Duolingo is fun and successful.

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066